

Prevalence and Antibiotic Resistance Patterns of Healthcare-Associated Infections at MCM Comprehensive Specialized Hospital in Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), infections acquired while receiving medical care, pose a significant risk to patients and remain a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Investigating the causative agents and their antimicrobial susceptibility profiles is essential to optimize the management and reduce the rate of these infections. However, there is a critical research gap in low-income settings, including Ethiopia. Therefore, this study aims to assess the prevalence, antimicrobial resistance patterns, and factors associated with HAIs at MCM Comprehensive Specialized Hospital in Ethiopia.

Methods: A retrospective chart review study was conducted among 414 patients admitted between January 1st and December 31st, 2022. Data were abstracted using a pre-tested, structured electronic questionnaire, which was then exported to SPSS V.20.0 software for analysis. Data were summarized using frequencies and percentages. To identify factors associated with the development of HAIs, a binary logistic regression model was fitted at 5% level of significance. Adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were used to interpret significant results.

Results: The prevalence of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) was 13% (54/414), with the most common infections being urinary tract infections (21/54) and hospital-acquired pneumonia (17/54). Among the 54 HAI cases, bacterial pathogens were detected and cultured in 34 patients. The most frequently identified bacteria were Coagulase-Negative Staphylococcus (9/34), Escherichia coli (8/34), and Enterococcus species (7/34). Antibiotic susceptibility testing revealed complete resistance to Ceftriaxone in 25/34 isolates and resistance to Cotrimoxazole in 33/34 isolates. Length of hospital stay exceeding 7 days, use of a urinary catheter, history of chronic respiratory disease, and previous antibiotic use were identified as significant factors associated with HAI development.

Conclusions: The prevalence of HAIs was high at MCMCSH. The common bacterial pathogens isolated exhibited high resistance to commonly prescribed antimicrobials. The findings highlight the importance of emphasizing early detection and management of infections, particularly in vulnerable patient populations, implementing comprehensive infection prevention protocols, reducing unnecessary hospital stays, rational antibiotic use with an antibiogram-guided therapy approach, and prioritizing targeted catheterization practices.

Key words: Healthcare-Associated Infection, Antibiotic Resistance Patterns, Retrospective chart review, Binary Logistic Regression, Ethiopia

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